
ISSUES OF ORGANIZING AUDIT IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article talks about the economic essence, classification and assessment of issues of organizing audit in the public sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key words. economic essence, classification and assessment, organization of audit activities in the public sector.

INTRODUCTION. In the early years of independence, special attention was paid to the organization of auditing in our Republic. In this regard, on December 9, 1992, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Auditing Activities" was adopted, and on May 26, 2000, a new edition of this Law "On Auditing Activities" was adopted and entered into force. Later, the legal basis for auditing activities was strengthened by a number of decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, it is stipulated in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-615 dated April 4, 2007 "On further improving the activities of audit organizations and increasing responsibility for the quality of services provided by them", Resolution No. PP-907 dated July 2, 2008 "On additional measures to increase the financial stability of audit organizations" and Resolution No. 274 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 12, 2017 "On additional measures to ensure further improvement of the legal framework for the activities of audit organizations". Important for the development of audit activities in our republic, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-3946 dated September 19, 2018 "On measures to further develop audit activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted. It set the task of improving the legislation on audit activities, including organizing them on the basis of international standards. The resolution indicates that there is a shortcoming in the country that "national standards for auditing do not fully comply with generally accepted international auditing standards, which does not ensure the formation of the ability of foreign investors to understand the truthfulness of the financial statements of local enterprises."

To improve the legislation on auditing activities in order to transition to international auditing standards, including the formation of an effective system of external control over the quality of work of auditing organizations, aimed at improving the quality of audit services and supporting the business community's confidence in the results of the work of auditing organizations, based on international standards;

to increase the level of involvement of auditing organizations in international auditing networks, including the organization of active methodological support for auditing organizations and auditors in the application of international auditing standards;

The priority areas were identified, such as cooperation between public associations of the republic and international organizations that set international auditing standards, as well as intensification of the activities of public associations of the republic to popularize the best world practices in the application of these standards.

The resolution provides for the organization and conduct of internal audits in the public sector, in addition to external audits conducted by international auditing organizations, the Accounts Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the Department of State Financial Control of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Also, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 24, 2015 No. 4720 “On measures to introduce modern corporate governance methods in joint-stock companies” strictly stipulates that “... in 2015-2018, all joint-stock companies must publish annual financial statements and conduct external audits in accordance with International Auditing Standards and International Financial Reporting Standards.”

What led to the need to transition to international auditing standards?

The integration of our country's economy into the world community, direct attraction of foreign investments, establishment of special economic zones creates the need to move to international standards of financial reporting and auditing.

LITERATURE REVIEW. International Standards of Auditing (ISAs) are developed by the International Auditing Practice Committee (IAPC) of the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC). IFAC was founded on October 7, 1977. This Federation includes national public accounting organizations from more than 100 countries around the world, including Uzbekistan.

The main principles of auditing activities in accordance with the International Standards of Auditing are: honesty, integrity, independence, confidentiality and thorough knowledge (competence).

100 numbers (positions) are assigned to each standardized object. Since there are 11 standardization objects, a total of 1,100 standards can be developed. Since there is no need for such a large number of standards in practice, most of them are not used. For example, the standardization object called "Planning" (300-399) consists of three standards: 300-"Planning", 310-"Business Knowledge", 320-

"Audit Rigor". Thus, 7 more standards can be adopted on planning issues. In addition, up to 10 substandards can be opened for each standard.

These standards play an important role in improving the quality and status of auditing activities on an international scale. These standards and norms are developed in several areas:

- a) international auditing standards;
- b) international management accounting codes of practice;
- c) international public sector norms.

IFAC organizes and implements all activities related to accounting and auditing through its committees. Currently, these include: an audit practice committee, a training committee, an ethics committee, a financial and management accounting committee, a planning committee, a public sector committee, and others.

Although auditors around the world perform essentially similar work, the organization of auditing activities in each country may have its own national characteristics. International standards and norms of auditing do not supersede national standards and norms of a particular country.

Many countries (Uzbekistan since 1999) are developing their own national standards and other regulatory documents. They have their own audit methodology, which is aimed at ensuring the basic requirements of IFAC.

Two professional organizations of accountants and auditors occupy a significant place in Europe. These are the International Accounting Standards Committee (IASC) and the Federation of European Accountants (FEE). FEE was founded on January 1, 1987, and its headquarters are located in Brussels.

National traditions, as well as public organizations of auditors, also play a huge role in the establishment and development of the auditing profession. For example, the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA) in America has had a huge impact on the development of auditing in the United States. It is entrusted with the following responsibilities:

- setting professional requirements for certified public accountants;
- conducting research and publishing literature on accounting and auditing topics;
- providing consulting services for the administration;
- providing consulting services in the field of taxation.

- Many other institutions, associations and institutes have also influenced the development of auditing. Each of them was created to perform certain tasks and has different approaches to auditing. Without a doubt, one of the most important is the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), which is responsible for the development of the financial market.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. This research work extensively covers the economic essence, classification and assessment of issues related to the organization of auditing in the public sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS. International Standards on Auditing (ISA) are international professional standards used in the implementation of auditing activities. The main purpose of the International Standards on Auditing (ISA) is to contribute to the development of the audit service in countries where the level of professionalism is lower than the world level and to form unified approaches.

What is the essence and purpose of auditing in the public sector?

According to T. M. Rogulenko, S. V. Ponomareva, A. V. Bodyako: Auditing in the public sector is an activity that consists in providing all interested parties with independent and objective information about economic events. It is a universal tool for the development of the economy, capable of effectively influencing the processes of economic development.

What are the tasks of organizing and conducting an audit in the public sector? The main task is the targeted use of budget funds. N. A. According to Kazakova (2019), the main tasks of auditing in the public sector are: studying the objectivity of the distribution of budget funds; checking the effectiveness of the use of budget funds; conducting an audit of the targeted and correct use of budget funds; developing a management strategy for the targeted use of funds; preparing information and reports on the results of the audit to the relevant bodies.

CONCLUSIONS. Analyzing and drawing conclusions from the above definitions, it can be concluded that in our country, the processes of deep changes, consistent reform and liberalization of all aspects of political and socio-economic life, democratic renewal and modernization of our society are developing at a rapid pace.

Theoretical issues of transition to international standards of auditing in the public sector of our country are covered. The work presents problems in organizing financial control and internal audit in ministries receiving funds from the budget. The results of internal audits in the public education system are analyzed. Proposals are made on the transition to international standards of auditing in the public sector.

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